

REHABILITATION AND REINTEGRATION SERVICES WITHIN THE SOCIAL WELFARE SYSTEM IN THE REPUBLIC OF SERBIA FOR WOMEN SURVIVORS OF VIOLENCE

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I. REHABILITATION AND REINTEGRATION SERVICES WITHIN THE SOCIAL WELFARE SYSTEM IN THE REPUBLIC OF SERBIA FOR WOMEN SURVIVORS OF VIOLENCE

1.1. Introduction

Violence against women has many short-term and long-term consequences to the health and welfare of women, as well as their overall quality of life, which can further influence their engagement in various aspects of life and society. The consequences violence leaves on women are frequently disregarded, while their specific needs remain unrecognized and unanswered. Therefore, this analysis aims at answering how the social welfare system in the Republic of Serbia can answer those needs (especially in regards to the existence or development of rehabilitation and reintegration services for women survivors of violence).

The draft of *Social Policies: Transposition of the EU Acquis Communautaire into the Laws and Policies of the Republic of Serbia*¹ analyzes reforms to the welfare system, which gives us a good framework for the situation in the Republic of Serbia. The general aim of the reforms to the welfare system as shown in the Draft Action Plan for Chapter 19 — Social Policies and Employment, which began in 2001, is to develop integrated social protections by developing services, securing plurality of service providers, and service quality and professional work. This process entails increasing the responsibilities of local governments and increasing the influence of various societal actors (public and civil sectors). Economic policies and the budget are a major influence on social policies. While the state is working on developing the social welfare system which incorporates all societal actors, local authorities are the ones who provide development programs, and establish and ensure that social welfare institutions function well. Non-governmental organizations have also been recognized as creators of social programs and projects, and as providers of social welfare services.

The Social Welfare Act (from 2011) stipulates that all citizens of the Republic of Serbia can equally exercise their rights and can equally access social welfare services. This Act defines the aims of social welfare as: minimal financial security and the individual's and family's independence in relation to meeting their basic needs; providing accessible service; creating equal opportunities for an independent life and encouraging social inclusion; preservation and advancement of family relations; advancement of family, gender and inter-generational solidarity; prevention of abuse, neglect or exploitation, and alleviation of their effects. The Act foresees that funds should be reallocated from the state budget to the local governments so as to finance services in local communities.

1 Tanja Ignjatovic, *Social Policies: Transposition of EU Acquis Communautaire into the Laws and Policies of the Republic of Serbia* (draft), 2020. Autonomous Women's Center.

The Action Plan notes that a Draft Amendment to the Social Welfare Act has been produced, and that it aims at a more just division of budget finances, more efficient social inclusion measures for everyone who is capable of work but receives financial aid, and a more targeted approach to social service users which would in turn produce greater adequacy of financial aid.

The Action Plan also provides an overview of centers for social work (public institutions which have, among others, been entrusted with providing social welfare services). On a state level there are 140 centers and 173 divisions. It also notes that activities have been undertaken in developing community services, but that despite efforts made by the state the overall situation has not improved. It's also to be noted that there is an increasing trend of children using social welfare services, an increase in the number of cases in relation to legal protection for families, and an increase in the number of cases in relation to violence. The Action Plan also notes that the network of service providers has to be expanded in local governments territories, so as to make the services equally accessible to all; and also that centers for social work must strengthen their capacities (especially due to the longstanding ban on hiring new employees in the public sector).

Currently, the new *Strategy for Developing Social Welfare in 2019-2025* is being developed, while the new *Strategy for Deinstitutionalization and Community Social Service Development* is being planned, as well as accompanying action plans. A process of standardization of social services and licensing of all service providers in the state sector is also foreseen, but there is no mention of licensing service providers in the non-governmental sector.

Serbia has ratified the *European Council Convention on Preventing and Combating Violence against Women and Domestic Violence* (2013), which entails legislative and other measures that provide protections and support to survivors of violence, thus aiming to also prevent further violence. These measures must be “based on an understanding of violence against women and domestic violence from a gender perspective, and they should focus on the victim’s human rights and safety; based on an integrated approach which takes into consideration the relations between the victim, the abuser, the children and their social environment; aimed at avoiding secondary victimization; aimed at strengthening women victims of violence and their economic independence; and where it’s appropriate, they must make sure that different services aimed at protecting and supporting the victim are provided in the same space, that those services shall be adequate in relation to the specific needs of victims, including children, and that they are accessible” (Article 18, paragraph 3). Service provision must not be dependent on the victim’s readiness to file charges or testify against her abuser (Article 18, paragraph 4). The Convention differentiates between two types of services: **general services** (Article 20) and **specialized support services** (Article 22).

1.2. Theme and aims of the analysis

The goal of this analysis was to map social welfare services intended for women surviving violence, as well as services intended for the overall population (and can therefore also be used by women surviving violence, or they as a group have been recognized as one of the main priority groups), in local government units and in the whole country.

1.3. Methodology, challenges and limits

The research procedure entailed:

- Gathering, reviewing and representation of analysis of social welfare services that have been produced thus far;
- Gathering information on, and reviewing services as defined by legal regulations (relevant laws and decisions on social welfare rights and services in each local government unit), and processing these on basis of quantity and quality.

The first limitation encountered in mapping social welfare services intended for women surviving violence was the total lack of a single, unified classification system of said services. We, therefore, took the classification as defined by the Social Welfare Act (Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia, number 24/2011). The same type of services were defined differently in various documents, and in some cases they were even classified in different categories — all of which made the subsequent analysis and classification all the more difficult.

Another limitation we encountered was the (total) lack of documents in some local government units. We only acquired a fifth of all Decisions on Social Welfare Rights and Services from the legal database *Paragraf Lexa* (which contains all existing regulations in the Republic of Serbia, as well as those pertaining to the level of local government units). Seeing as there is a large number of documents available for every local government unit, and that acquiring Decisions on Social Welfare Rights and Services would require a long time, we sent an e-request to all units of local government and asked them to submit their valid Decisions on Social Welfare Rights and Services. Many of the local government units do not have the latest updated version of the valid document version so they sent original documents with all subsequent additions and amendments, which further extended the process of gathering and processing data. We gathered and analyzed documents from 118 units of local government out of the total of 174 in the Republic of Serbia.

2. OVERVIEW OF ANALYSES OF REHABILITATION AND REINTEGRATION SERVICES MADE THUS FAR IN THE REPUBLIC OF SERBIA

2.1. Analyses of specialized services for women who have survived violence

There are several analyses in Serbia which map social welfare services (among others, reintegration and rehabilitation services intended for women who are surviving violence, or services which they may use as well). In the following section we will show results of analyses conducted thus far (with a separate section pertaining to services for women with disabilities and Roma women who are surviving violence).

Based on the *Independent Report on The Implementation of the European Council Convention on Preventing and Combating Violence against Women and Domestic Violence “Improved Legislation — Failed Protection”*² it may be concluded that Serbia’s legal regulations lack a single, unified classification of services. The classification of welfare services as defined by the Social Welfare Act does not make the distinction between general and specialized services (as foreseen by the Convention). There is also no single, unified and publicly accessible base/map of services (for women surviving violence); Rulebooks have not been made, and standards for providing specialized services have not been produced; there is no sustainable financing of services, but rather they are financed sporadically and from project to project. Access to services is limited in relation to:

- Accessibility for women who belong to several marginalized groups (especially for women with disability, Roma women, and lesbians)
- Geographic coverage (some local governments provide specialized services, some don’t)
- Finances (some service providers even request that beneficiaries participate in financing of said services)
- Administrative-formal level (some services are direct (SOS lines), while some require a referral (e.g. In order to be placed in a safe house the Center for Social Welfare must make a referral).

When it comes to service providers, it is evident that state owned service providers are favored in comparison to those from the non-governmental sector.

2 Tanja Ignjatovic and Vanja Macanovic, *Improved Legislation — Failed Protection, an Independent Report on the Implementation of the European Council Convention on Preventing and Combating Violence against Women and Domestic Violence*, 2018. Autonomous Women’s Center. Available in Serbian at: https://www.womenngo.org.rs/images/GREVIO/GREVIO_Izvestaj_SRP.pdf (accessed on: 28.3.2020).

The publication “*Protection and Support for Women with Experiences of Violence — An Analysis of Local Policies in the Republic of Serbia*”³ takes a look at support services intended for women with experiences of violence. At the beginning of the publication there is a list of basic characteristics and classification of said services; they are then analyzed in relation to the minimal recommended standards; an overview of international standards is given and used as reference for establishing and providing services; then European support services are mapped and good practice examples given. Among the good practice examples — those pertaining to rehabilitation and reintegration services — in Europe we should take note of: the National budget line for service provision and project funding (for protection from domestic violence) (Scotland); Shelter development program (Scotland); One national and five regional resource centers (Norway).

In the second part there is an overview of Serbia’s system of support services for women with experiences of violence. It looks into the policies from 6 local government units (city of Vranje, municipality of Kikinda, city of Krusevac, city of Novi Sad, city of Nis, and city of Uzice). This section ends with the conclusion that the number of services is inadequate (especially so for specialized services), that they are not adequately distributed geographically, and that they are not easily accessible. It also notes that standards pertaining to specialized services are not adequate, while the service procurement system is not well regulated (and that state service providers are favored in comparison to those in the private sector). When it comes to protection and support programs for women surviving violence in regards to financial and psychosocial support, social housing, employment and childcare, they are deemed to be one dimensional, mutually incongruent and disconnected. There is a lack of support programs available to women who leave the abuser — programs in relation to social and health protection, employment, housing and childcare. These types of services have not been planned for, while the local government’s existing financial resources are not adequately used. Women who are surviving violence are usually offered to be displaced from their home, while economic, social and psychological programs aimed at increasing the woman’s independence, are rarely employed.

2.2. Analyses of services provided to women with disability who have survived violence

There are only a few analyses of services intended for people with disabilities, and they do not provide statewide data but rather focus only on a limited number of local government units. In the *Special Report of the Ombudsman “Accessibility for All”*⁴ which aimed at mapping the accessibility of services for people with disabilities (in general), mapping accessibility of municipal buildings, social service buildings, hospitals, and retirement services buildings in 26 local government areas⁵. This

3 Danijela Pesic, *Protection and Support for Women with Experiences of Violence — An Analysis of Local Policies in the Republic of Serbia*, 2016. Autonomous Women’s Center, Belgrade. Available in Serbian at: https://www.womenngo.org.rs/images/publikacije-dp/2016/Zastita_i_podrska_za_zene_sa_iskustvom_nasilja-analiza_lokalnih_politika_u_Republici_Srbiji.pdf (accessed on: 28.2.2020)

4 Special Report of the Ombudsman “Accessibility for All”, 2018. Ombudsman. Available in Serbian at: <https://www.ombudsman.rs/attachments/article/5893/Posebna%20izvestaj%20PRISTUPACNOSTI%20final.pdf> (accessed on 28.2.2020.)

5 Data was analyzed in the following municipalities/cities: Apatin, Zabalj, Mionica, Svilajnac, Aleksinac, Zrenjanin, Nis, Sombor, Bela Palanka, Jagodina, Pirot, Subotica, Blace, Kanjiza, Pozarevac, Topola, Brus, Kraljevo, Prokuplje, Trstenik, Vladicin Han, Lebane, Raska, Dimitrovgrad, Leskovac, Ruma.

report finds that activities intended to ensure service accessibility to people with disability are done *ad hoc*, from time to time and are initiated by individuals from the local government, associations of people with disabilities, civil society organizations, or result from donations granted to certain projects. Relevant institutions focus on removing architectural barriers, while the information barrier problem remains out of view. Overcoming the problem of architectural barriers (setting up ramps, banisters, elevator platforms, lowering counters) is often done without thought to harmonizing everything with widely accepted accessibility standards and the real needs of people with disabilities. It's worrisome that new buildings are being raised, or old ones reconstructed, without adequate implementation of accessibility standards (thus violating the basic principles of the UN Convention on The Rights of People with Disabilities). Monitoring has shown that there are rarely any cases where assistive listening systems have been installed or where people who know sign language have been employed (four out of 104 buildings have installed inductive loops, while only two people who know sign language have been employed).

*The Report on Accessibility of Support Structures for Women with Disability Who Have Experienced Violence*⁶ analyzed institutions which provide support to women who experience violence in the health field (hospitals and clinical centers), judiciary (courts and public prosecution offices), social welfare (centers for social work, safe houses, marriage and family counseling) and security (police stations) in 7 local governments units⁷ in Vojvodina. Accessibility of services was assessed in relation to several criteria: availability of informational materials (Braille) and web sites for the blind and partially sighted women; availability of informational materials in institutions/organizations which work with women with disability; cooperation with organizations which work with women with disability; services pertaining to domestic violence provided and adapted for women with disability; physical accessibility; architectural accessibility; transportation for women with disability; staff trained in sign language, etc., and therefore able to communicate with women with disability; employment of women with disability in organizations/institutions; specialized trainings for staff on the status of women with disability and gender based violence; fundraising so as to make services accessible to women with disability; forwarding domestic violence reports to relevant institutions/processing these cases; investigating suspicions of domestic violence suffered by women with disability and taking required measures. Results show that institutions in larger cities are more willing than those in smaller municipalities to cooperate with civil society organizations to improve accessibility of services for women with disabilities that are aimed at protecting them from domestic violence, and that these big city institutions are also better informed on institutional obligations foreseen by international conventions. Furthermore, when it comes to accessibility for the blind or nearsighted people (Braille) only 14.8 % of institutions have materials in Braille or simple text, and only 22.2 % of institutions have an accessible web site. Employees at institutions who provide support service are inadequately informed about barriers which have to be removed, about gender-based violence and existing support services (outside of institutions) which accessible to women with disabilities. Representatives of two thirds (74%) of

6 The Report on Accessibility of Support Structures for Women with Disability Who Have Experienced Violence, ...Out of Circle, Vojvodina, UN Women, European Commission.

7 Novi Sad, Zrenjanin, Sombor, Subotica, Sremska Mitrovica, Vrsac and Kikinda (that is just for the area of Vojvodina).

institutions conclude that their services are accessible to women with disabilities, based on criteria that every woman (with or without disability) is treated equally. Even though representatives of institutions usually believe they are physically accessible (81%) and architecturally adapted (62%) this data is in direct contrast to what women with disabilities have witnessed in the field — they note that the most common barrier is in fact the physical/architectural inaccessibility of institutions and services. Also, they note that ramps are frequently not functional, that there are cases where there is an accessible entrance into an institution but there is no elevator or that it's not adapted to women with vision impairments (tactile lanes, signal stairs and the like). In relation to employment of people who have been trained in sign language, only 7% have employed such people, while half of institutions note that they employ women with disabilities. In relation to financing services intended for women with disabilities, 57% of representatives note that they try to secure finances that are used to make services more accessible to women with disabilities.

2.3. Analyses of services for Roma women who have survived violence

The publication “*Gender Based Violence against Roma Women and Accessibility of Support Services*”⁸ gives an overview of research which focused on centers for social work, police stations and schools in 5 units of local government⁹. The publication notes that Roma women are one of the most vulnerable social groups, discriminated both in the public and private spheres. They are physically and socially isolated in neighborhoods on the outskirts of cities where sanitation and security are at a low level; they are not well educated and have language barriers to overcome as well. Legally they are invisible because they often do not have personal documents (ID cards, etc.). Seeing as they usually live in unsanitary neighborhoods, they frequently face numerous problems: lack of drinking water, no adequate sewage system; living in unsafe housing, they also frequently share their living space with two or more people. Women and girls are particularly vulnerable due to the strict patriarchal structure permeating the Roma community, and they live in extreme psychological and physical isolation, independent movement is forbidden to them (without a male escort), while at the same time they are also expected to find ways to meet their everyday needs (for instance, to find water). These factors make Roma women additionally susceptible to domestic violence. Another problem are forced marriages and early motherhood. They rarely report violence due to a strict patriarchal upbringing that teaches them to submit to men, and that in turn normalizes violence. And also due to the fact that they have nowhere to go.

The research shows that institutions which provide services to women who have survived violence are places where Roma women face prejudice, and that professionals working in these institutions don't have adequate knowledge on working with women and girls from marginalized groups. From all the services listed in this research, Roma women have identified the following needs and have assessed the level of their satisfaction with services: gynecological exams (89.3%),

8 Jelena Marinkovic, Nada Durickovic, Amela Bicic, *Gender Based Violence against Roma Women and Accessibility of Services*, 2019. Roma Center for Women and Children, Daje, Belgrade. Available in Serbian at: http://romadaje.org/images/1576231681_RBN%2Bnad%2BRomkinjama%2Bi%2Busluge%2Bpodr%25C5%25A1ke.pdf (accessed on 28.3.2020).

9 The research was conducted in the municipalites of Kragujevac, Kostolac, Smederevska Palanka, Mladenovac and Belgrade municipalites of Vozdovac, Palilula, Zemun and Zvezdara.

consultations with social workers/psychologist at CSWs (68.2%), free legal aid (69.2%), financial benefits for children (85.7%), financial aid (56.6%), SOS consultations (30.6%), safe house sheltering (11.2%). When it comes to specialized support services, women stressed that they did not take advantage of the SOS consultations because they don't know the phone number, while those who were sheltered in a safe house noted that they were discriminated in relation to personal hygiene, theft, number of children and length of stay.

2.4. Support services for victims of violent felonies

The publication “*Overview of Existing Organizations Providing Support in Serbia*”¹⁰ takes a look at support services from the perspective of the European Parliament's and Council's Directive of October 25th 2012 on determining minimal standards on the rights, support and protection of victims of felonies (Directive on Victims' Rights). Serbia has made the implementation of this Directive a priority as part of the EU accession process. Classification of services based on the Directive on Victims' Rights (which this publication is based on) is not complementary to the service classification foreseen by the Council of Europe's Convention, neither is it complementary to the Social Welfare Act of the Republic of Serbia. It can, however, be a source of information about where women (who have survived violence) can turn to for support (by using a map of services intended for victims of criminal acts).

The Directive stipulates that the state should ensure free access to organizations providing support, and should act in the victim's interest before, during and a certain time after felony judicial proceedings. This report is based on a poll where 73 organizations were interviewed, while information from another 36 organizations was added to the database. Existing organizations in Serbia were polled and an analysis was made in regards to what needs to be done so as to secure that victims of all forms of criminality, on the whole territory of Serbia, have access to services.

The report goes on to say that the number of general services available to victims of all types of criminal acts in Serbia is limited, that the services are frequently specific and focused on specific victim profiles (women with disability as victims of violence, victims of gender-based violence, trafficking victims, etc.). Even though this level of specialization is important and meaningful especially for women from particularly vulnerable groups, there is a risk that numerous victims who are not part of those groups will not get the support they need. Also, services are limited in regards to geographical coverage and most are available on a local level. The general conclusion the report comes to is that many victims in Serbia are at a risk of not being able to exercise their right to access services.

10 *Overview of Existing Organizations Providing Support in Serbia*, 2017. Multi-funder trust fund for the support of the judiciary in Serbia. Available in English at: <https://www.mdtfjss.org.rs/archive//file/Overview%20of%20existing%20victim%20support%20services%20in%20Serbia%20-%20RS.pdf> (accessed on 28.3.2020).

3. OVERVIEW OF SERVICES DEFINED ON THE BASIS OF RELEVANT EXISTING REGULATIONS

The Social Welfare Act of the Republic of Serbia distinguishes five categories of social services (Article 40):

- 1) Assessment and planning services;
- 2) Daily community services;
- 3) Support for independent living services;
- 4) Consultation-therapy and socio-educational services;
- 5) Accommodation services.

Children, youth, adults and seniors are recognized as beneficiaries of rights and services of social welfare.

Aside from the already mentioned social welfare services, we will also analyze the financial aid rights in local government units, since this type of right may be very important in regards to reintegration of women survivors of domestic and partner violence.

In the following sections we will provide an analysis of services provided in local government units as defined by the Decisions on Social Welfare Rights and Services, and its amendments. This analysis encompasses 118 units of local governments¹¹. The remaining 56 local government units did not make the data available, that is, did not provide the documents.

Before we set out to analyze the services in local government units, we once again remind the reader of the limitations faced in mapping and analyzing data (chapter 1.3).

11 This analysis encompasses Decisions on Social Welfare Rights and Services, and its amendments in the following local government units: Ada, Aleksandrovac, Aleksinac, Arandelovac, Arilje, Babusnica, Bac, Backa Palanka, Backa Topola, Bajina Basta, Batocina, Becej, Bela Palanka, Beocin, Beograd, Blace, Bogatic, Boljevac, Bor, Brus, Bujanovac, Cacak, Cajetina, Crna Trava, Dimitrovgrad, Doljevac, Gadzin Han, Golubac, Gornji Milanovac, Indija, Irig, Jagodina, Kanjiza, Kikinda, Kladovo, Knic, Knjazevac, Koceljeva, Kosjeric, Kovacica, Kovin, Kragujevac, Kraljevo, Krupanj, Krusevac, Kucevo, Kula, Kursumlija, Lajkovac, Lapovo, Leskovac, Loznica, Lucani, Majdanpek, Mali Idos, Mali Zvornik, Malo Crnice, Medveda, Merosina, Negotin, Nis, Nova Crnja, Nova Varos, Novi Pazar, Novi Sad, Odzaci, Opovo, Osecina, Pancevo, Paracin, Pecinci, Petrovac na Mlavi, Pirot, Pozarevac, Prijepolje, Prokuplje, Raca, Raska, Razanj, Rekovac, Ruma, Sabac, Secanj, Senta, Sid, Sjenica, Smederevo, Sokobanja, Sombor, Srbobran, Sremska Mitrovica, Stara Pazova, Subotica, Svrlijig, Temerin, Titel, Topola, Trgoviste, Trstenik, Ub, Uzice, Valjevo, Varvarin, Velika Plana, Veliko Gradiste, Vladicin Han, Vladimirci, Vlasotince, Vranje, Vrnjacka Banja, Vrsac, Zabalj, Zabari, Zagubica, Zajecar, Zitiste, Zrenjanin.

A total of 29 units of local government did not provide the requested documentation: Aleksinac, Alibunar, Apatin, Backi Petrovac, Bela Crkva, Bojnik, Bosilegrad, Cicevac, Coka, Cuprija, Despotovac, Ivanjica, Lebane, Ljig, Ljubovija, Mionica, Novi Becej, Novi Knezevac, Plandiste, Pozega, Presevo, Priboj, Smederevska Palanka, Sremski Karlovci, Surdulica, Svilajnac, Tutin, Vrbas, Zitorada.

3.1. Assessment and planning services

This type of service is defined by the Social Welfare Act (Article 43) as a service which encompasses assessment of the situation, needs, strengths and risks of the beneficiary and other important people in their life; and producing:

- a) A service plan and measures for the family and a permanence plan for the child;
- b) A plan for independent living of a young person who was left without parental care before turning 14, that is, didn't live with their parents or guardians;
- c) An individual service plan and measures for an adult or senior beneficiary.

Providing this service has been entrusted to centers for social work, the Center for Family Accommodation and Adoption, and institutions for the upbringing of children and youth.

3.2. Daily community services

The Social Welfare Act distinguishes 4 types of daily community (Article 40) services:

- 1) Daily accommodation;
- 2) Help at the home;
- 3) Shelter;
- 4) Other services which support a beneficiary within a family context and in the immediate environment.

Table 1 — Daily community services in relation to the number of local government unit

Name of service	General populace that needs assistance	For defined categories	For women victims of violence
Daily accommodation/ Club	/	99	/
Help and care at home	18	96	/
Child's personal companion	/	74	/
Shelter	/	7	/
Other services	3	1	/

Analysis of daily community services in local government units has shown that **there are no local government units that offer daily services intended for women who have survived violence**. They can use some of the other daily services as members of other groups (youth, adults and seniors, women with disabilities), but there is no specialized service intended for women surviving violence.

When it comes to the **daily accommodation** / club service, from the analyzed Decisions on Social Welfare Rights and Services, it can be concluded that this type of service is offered by 99 units of local government. All units provide this service for certain categories of people. Among others for:

- People with disabilities (most often defined as people with mental disabilities)
- Adults and seniors (with disabilities, with dementia, with an illness)
- Children and youth (with disabilities, autism, cerebral palsy and child paralysis, at risk children / children that may be in conflict with the law / with behavioral problems / kindergarten aged children).

The **help and care at home service** is provided by local government units for the following categories of beneficiaries:

- a) The overall populace generally in one local government unit.
- b) 96 local government units provide it for categories that are differently defined, among others for: seniors, children and youth, people with chronic illnesses, people who live alone and cannot take care of themselves, children who are involved in the correctional process at home.
- c) 17 local government units provide help and care at home services for beneficiary categories that have not been defined in advance, that is, to categories that are defined as “others who are not able to take care of themselves, but live alone; or other vulnerable groups, in accordance with the community’s needs; or as people who reside in the local government unit’s territory but who have limited physical and psychological capabilities making them unable to live independently in their home without regular help in everyday activities, care and oversight, while family support is insufficient or not available; people who are more closely defined by the local government’s Rulebook”.

The **child’s personal companion** service is foreseen by 74 local government units. This service is intended for children with disabilities who need support in satisfying basic everyday needs in regards to movement, personal hygiene, feeding, dressing and communication with others. It is provided to children who are enrolled in an educational institution, that is, in a school, and it entails: help at home for dressing and maintaining personal hygiene, help in community life — using public transportation, mobility, going to places where the child spends their free time, etc. Local government units note that this service was on average provided for 40 hours a week. This service can be classified as a service intended for independent living, but all local government

units classify it as a daily service since it is provided daily to children who attend kindergarten/school.

The daily **shelter** services is defined by 7 local government units and it is provided for the following categories: children, youth, adults and seniors who live or work on the street or who voluntarily request or accept the service.

Three local government units foresee **other services which support beneficiaries within a family context and in the immediate environment**. Among others, these services encompass:

- 1) *The Center for Hypo-rehabilitation* — 2 local government units offer this service to an open group of beneficiaries, that is, to children and youth with mental disability, children with autism, children with behavioral problems, and adults who fulfil the requirements for this service (depending on the type and degree of mental disability).
- 2) *Services which support beneficiaries within the family context and immediate environment* — this service is available in 1 local government unit and is intended for anyone in the local unit.
- 3) *Inclusive playrooms* — intended for children up to 11 years of age, with or without disability.

3.3. Independent living services

The Social Welfare Act distinguishes 4 types of daily community services (Article 40):

- 1) Assisted living
- 2) Personal assistance
- 3) Training for independent living
- 4) Other types of support necessary for active participation in society.

Table 2 — Independent living support services in relation to the number of local government units

Name of service	General populace that needs assistance	For defined categories	For women victims of violence
Personal assistance	/	38	/
Assisted living	/	56	1
Social accommodation in protected conditions	27	32	6 ¹²
Other services	/	5	/

12 This service is not intended only for victims of violence but other categories as well, but victims of violence are just one of the many listed. Also, all local government units have intended this service for all victims of violence, not just women.

An analysis of the **independent living service** provided by local government units shows that **only one unit of local government offers this service specifically to women who have survived violence (and their children), while they are noted as the direct beneficiary for other particular services** (which will be further explained when we map the services themselves).

The **personal assistance** service is defined by the Decisions of 38 local government units. This service is intended for adults with disabilities who need 1st or 2nd degree of support and who also receive additional finances intended for help and care, under the condition that they are capable of making their own decisions and that they are either employed or active in the community, or enrolled in an educational program. This service is aimed at maintaining and improving the beneficiary's quality of life, depending on their needs and capacity to independently conduct themselves in certain everyday activities, as well as to improve the beneficiary's family's capacity and available resources. It is geared toward satisfying personal needs and real-life situations, so as to develop a greater level of independence.

When it comes to **assisted living** this service is defined by the Decisions of 57 local government units (out of which only 1 has intended this service for women surviving). The only local government unit that has assisted living available to women who have survived violence, and their children, is the city of Zrenjanin. This service type also includes the service of **Prolonged Accommodation for Women and Children Victims of Domestic Violence and Victims of Trafficking**, which is provided by the city of Zrenjanin. It is provided to women and children victims of domestic violence and victims of trafficking, who live on the territory of Zrenjanin, after security risks have ceased and there is no further need for them to be placed in a safe house, and in case they don't have any housing or they have temporary housing.

In other local government units this service is intended for various beneficiary categories:

- a) Youth who are becoming more independent are temporarily provided this service along with support services for developing skills necessary for complete independence and incorporation into the community. These young people are placed in housing specifically intended for this purpose, and only once they no longer have accommodation at center for social welfare institutions or with a foster family, as well as after accommodations are no longer available with an upbringing institution, that is, after leaving a detention facility; it is also provided to those who cannot or will not go back to their biological family or kin, and are not able to begin living independently;
- b) Adults with disabilities who, due to societal or other barriers, have limited possibilities to get involved in society on par with everyone else. It is provided to those are no longer in an institution, and may be organized as an alternative to institutionalization, for a duration that suits the beneficiary's needs;
- c) Recovering alcoholics or drug users, 18 years or older.

When it comes to **social housing in protected circumstances** many local government units classify this service under services for independent living, while others classify it in innovative ways or under other services. A total of 65 units provides this service, as follows:

- 1) 38 local government units provide it to defined beneficiary categories:
 - Seniors (65 years of age or older, capable of independent living);
 - People with disabilities (children with mental disability who are a beneficiary of financial assistance for help and caring);
 - single parents (single parents of minor children — father unknown, or mother unknown; if the other parent is not helping financially because they are deceased or because their residents is unknown, or because the other parent has been incarcerated for more than 6 months);
 - Individuals, and their families, who don't have housing but are residents of the municipality; people who as minors were under state protection (fostering, institutionalization);
 - Refugees and internally displaced persons; one parent families with a child/children under the age of 18 and/or a student/students under the age of 26;
 - People in dire financial need and their families who due to physical or mental disability, chronic illness or a family member's disability cannot provide for a decent life;
 - Younger adults who don't have parents.
 - 6 local government units list **victims of violence as beneficiaries of social housing services**, defined as: a person who was subject to violence in the family (city of Belgrade, Uzice, Pozarevac); as victims of sexual or family violence (Prijepolje, Smederevo); victims of family violence (Trgoviste).
- 2) A total of 27 local government units define the beneficiary group in categories but also leave a wider ranging definition as "other people who the CSW deems admissible".

Other services for independent living encompass: social entrepreneurship; organizations that assist people with mental disabilities; translation services for sign language for people with disabilities; training for independent living; additional support in the education of children, students and adults with mental disabilities within their groups and schools.

3.4. Counseling-therapy and socio-educational services

The Social Welfare Act lists the following as being counseling-therapy and socio-educational services:

- 1) Intensive services to families in crisis;
- 2) Counseling and support for parents, foster parents, parents who adopted children;
- 3) Support for families which take care of their child or adult family member with mental disability;
- 4) Maintaining family relations and family reconnection;

- 5) Counseling and support in cases of violence;
- 6) Family therapy;
- 7) Mediation;
- 8) SOS phone line;
- 9) Activation and other counseling and educational services and activities.

Table 3 — Counseling-therapy and socio-educational services in relation to the number of local government units

Name of service	General populace who need assistance	For defined categories	For victims of violence	
			Everyone	Women
Socio-educational services	22	3	/	/
Counseling services	34	40	15 ¹³	/
Therapy services	12	6	/	/
Mediation	26	/	/	/
Mobile team for emergency interventions	11	/	1	/
SOS line for victims of violence	6	3	4	1
Other services	12	4	/	/

Classification and analysis of **counseling-therapy and socio-educational services** shows that local government units in their Decisions on Social Welfare Rights and Services have classified and defined these services in very different ways, there is no overlap, there is mixing and varying degrees of generalization (in the sense that some services were defined just generally as counseling or therapy work, while some note specifically what group it applies to). For all of these reasons, the above shown table has its limitations, differences and deviations for some local government units. That also means that certain services must be analyzed further so as to ascertain the degree to which they are accessible to women who survive violence.

When it comes to **socio-educational services**, 22 local government units have intended this service for everyone on their territory, while 3 units of local government have clearly defined the categories for which the service is intended.

¹³ This service is intended for a wider group but victims of violence are included.

Counseling services are available to everyone in 33 local government units, while 55 local government units have clearly defined categories of people:

- For families in crisis (that is, family counseling, maintaining family relations and reconnecting families)
- For parents, foster parents, and parents who have adopted
- For children and youth (for adolescents, pre-kindergarten aged children, children with risky or delinquent behavior)
- For seniors
- In cases of domestic violence¹⁴
- Support for families which take care of a child/adult family member who has a mental disability
- Counseling for women¹⁵ (support for women from “vulnerable” groups who are exposed to stress or problems on a daily basis, or have suddenly been confronted with change or a problem in their family or environment)
- Office for the care of single mothers and mothers who take care of their child independently and directly¹⁶.

When it comes to **therapy services**, 12 local government units have intended this service for everyone, while 6 local government units have intended this service for families, that is, as family therapy.

According to the Decisions on Social Welfare **mediation** services are available in 26 local government units.

The **mobile team for emergency interventions** is available in 11 local government units and is open for everyone, while only one local government unit explicitly notes that this team is intended for victims of violence.

The **SOS phone** line service is offered in 14 local government units and is listed in their Decisions on Social Welfare Rights and Services. 6 local government units have intended this service for everyone, or they have not clearly defined what category it is intended for but have rather just noted that they offer the service. Those local government units are: Backa Topola, Kikinda, Raska, Trstenik, Kovacica, Leskovac. 3 local government units offer this service to individuals and families in crisis (Bela Palanka, Subotica, Indija). 4 local government units offer the service to victims of violence in general (Babusnica, Bogatic, Dimitrovgrad, Zitiste). Only one local

14 Aleksandrovac, Becej, Kikinda, Kladovo, Knic, Knjazevac, Leskovac, Pozarevac, Trstenik, Kovacica, Kosjeric, Lucani, Novi Sad, Srbobran, Vladicin Han.

15 Cajetina

16 Jagodina

government unit notes that women with experiences of gender-based violence are the intended group (Cajetina).

Other counseling-therapy and socio-educational services have been mapped in 12 local government units, where they are offered to everyone — activation and other counseling and educational services and activities (3 local government units), and legal support for marginalized groups in general (in 9 local government units). This type of service intended for clearly defined groups is available in 4 local government units, and consists of legal support for Roma people, people with disabilities, people in financial need, refugees and displaced people (1 local unit); Family colleague (two units of local government); and prevention and protection for victims of violence (1 local government unit).

3.5. Accommodation services

Accommodation services are defined in the Social Welfare Act (Article 40) as:

- 1) Accommodation in a home where their extended family lives, a foster family or another family for people who are older or elderly;
- 2) Accommodation in an institution;
- 3) Accommodation in a halfway house.

Table 4 — Accommodation services in relation to the number of local government units

Name of service	General populace who need assistance	For defined categories	For victims of violence	
			Everyone	Women
Accommodation in a halfway house, etc.	7	14	50 ¹⁷	19 ¹⁸
Safe house for victims of violence	/	/	4	8
Short term and sporadic accommodation	/	23	/	/
Other services	/	3	/	/

17 Within this group there is a certain number of local government units who offer the halfway house service to various categories, among others to victims of violence in general.

18 Within this group there is a certain number of local government units who offer the halfway house service to various categories, among others, women and children victims of violence.

When it comes to the service of **accommodation on a halfway house/similar unit**, the analyzed Decisions on Social Welfare Rights and Services has shown that 90 local government units define this service, out of which a total of 19 local government units intend the service for women victims of violence, while 50 local government units define it more widely as victims of violence (among others). The local government units that offer accommodation services to various groups, define those groups as follows:

- Children and youth (with no parental care, with behavioral problems, truancy, with no oversight and in various critical situations);
- Truancy (homeless people, beggars);
- Adults, seniors and people with disabilities;
- People who need emergency accommodation due to violence, neglect, natural disaster, fire, death of their caretaker;
- Pregnant women and women with children (one of which is younger than three years of age);
- Victims of domestic violence.

In local governments where victims of violence were listed as a category which can be placed in a halfway house it remains unclear whether they are placed in the same house as people from all other categories. (We have also noticed that some local government units use the term “halfway house/halfway station” when referring to cases where they send victims of violence to another unit’s safe house). A total of 19 Decisions on Social Welfare Rights and Services explicitly notes that the service is available to women and children who are in danger due to domestic violence (Babusnica, Beocin, Dimitrovgrad, Jagodina, Kladovo, Knic, Knjazevac, Nis, Novi Sad, Rekovac, Titel, Kursumila, Negotin, Nova Crnja, Svrlijig, Zabari, Leskovac, Secanj, Temerin).

The service of **safe house accommodation** for victims of violence is offered in 12 local government units. 8 units offer it explicitly to women and children victims of domestic violence (Belgrade, Kikinda, Pancevo, Ruma, Sremska Mitrovica, Vranje, Zrenjanin, Bor), while 4 offer it to victims of violence in general (Sabac, Smederevo, Subotica, Zajecar).

The service of **short term and temporary accommodation** is offered in 23 local government units. This service entails a short term stay that may happen sporadically and is offered to people with mental disabilities. A person may stay for a day, over the weekend, or for several days, thus securing support for the beneficiary as well as his/her family and allowing for an increase in their quality of life. Beneficiaries are people of all ages who have mental disabilities or autism, have multiple mental disabilities, or sensory and physical disability.

Other services include services of emergency shelter, such as: a social protection institution or foster family which is prepared for urgent accommodation of victims of violence, abuse and neglect, as well as seniors; for children — emergency placement in a family.

3.6. Financial aid

Financial aid is defined as a social welfare right. The Social Welfare Act (Article 79) defines financial aid as “financial social aid, additional finances for help and care, increased additional finances for help and care, assistance for enabling one to work, one-time financial aid, aid that can be given in goods or other types of material support, in accordance with this law and regulations adopted for its implementation”. Seeing as this legal classification diverges from the financial aid given by local government units, it will not be taken into consideration (or made comparison to). In the Decisions on Social Welfare Rights and Services we can find numerous and various rights pertaining to financial aid. Roughly we can classify them as follows:

- 1) Financial aid — money
- 2) Financial aid in goods
- 3) Reimbursement of expenses
- 4) Other rights

Table 5 — Financial aid in relation to the number of local governments

Name of service	Under the conditions defined by decisions of the LGU	
	One time	
Financial aid — money	One time	113
	In exceptional cases	21
	Emergency	13
	Other	42

The service of **financial aid — money** is differently classified so a “rough” division was made into several categories. It’s important to note that for some rights it was exceedingly difficult to make a clear distinction because they intertwine and are differently defined between government units, but the categories remain similar to each other. All types of financial aid (**one time, on exceptional occasions/emergency**) are provided so as to secure fulfilment of various social needs proceeding from various circumstances (unemployment and inability to satisfy basic needs; acquiring personal documents so as to exercise their social welfare rights, as well as expenses pertaining to starting and maintaining administrative and court cases, illness — the treatment of which isn’t completely covered by health insurance, placement in a social welfare institution or a foster family; assistance after leaving prison; fixing damages after a natural disaster, and the like). **Other financial aid** contains various types of help which differ in relation to timing and duration (continuous, temporary, monthly); those which are intended for different target groups (pensioners, parental aid for mothers, pregnant women, women who have just given birth, families of fallen soldiers, families in dire financial need, students, etc.). Women survivors of violence can use the financial aid services in accordance with the requirements stipulated in the Decisions on Social Welfare, as can others who reside on the territory of those

local governments. Financial aid — money — intended explicitly for victims of violence is a service offered in the city of Belgrade and Pirot.

Table 6 — Aid in goods in relation to the number of local government units

Name of service	Under conditions set out in decisions of LGU
	Free meals/state provided meals 80
	Food and hygiene packages 6
	New Year's presents for children 7
	Heating materials 14
Aid in goods	School textbooks and school supplies 18
	Equipping beneficiary for stay in social welfare institution or foster family 94
	Generally defined as aid in goods 20

The **aid in goods** service provides free meals through a state sponsored meal program or meals provided in schools; packages of food and hygiene products; New Year's presents for kids, heating materials (firewood, etc.), school textbooks and school supplies; equipment/clothes/etc. needed for placement in a social welfare institution or foster family. In 20 local government units this right is defined as a right to receive aid in goods, while the Decisions go into more detail. Women surviving violence are not explicitly noted as beneficiaries of this service, but they can use it pursuant to the Decision on Social Welfare Rights and Services, just as can other people residing in that local government unit.

Table 7 — Right to reimbursement of expenses in relation to the number of local government units

Name of service	Under conditions set out in decisions of LGU
	Funeral/burial expenses 105
	Transportation subsidy 55
	School trip subsidy 14
	Court expenses/expert testimony 4
Right to reimbursement of expenses	Public utilities 27
	Health care 26
	Accommodation 19
	Housing issues/adaptations 21
	Nutrition of vagrants 32

The **reimbursement of expenses service** is provided for: funerals/burial expense; transportation subsidies or as a discount on transportation for various types of beneficiaries (young and older students, pensioners, people with disabilities, children with disabilities and their companions, professors, war veterans with disabilities and victims of war, people with health insurance, people in temporary accommodation); school trip subsidies (excursions, summer vacations, winter vacations for children in dire financial need, children with disabilities, etc.); court case expenses/expert testimony; public utilities (or discounts on public utilities); healthcare insurance (also for specific medical procedures for children with disabilities, rehabilitation for youth, specific nutritional needs of children, in vitro fertilization, acquisition of orthopedic equipment that is not covered by the Republic Fund for Healthcare of the Republic of Serbia); accommodation (boarding school for children in dire financial need, children with disabilities, emergency accommodation in shelters, etc.); solving housing issues, assistance in sanitizing and improving/adapting existing housing of people in dire financial need; nutrition and travel expense for vagrants. Women surviving violence can use this service the same as any other citizens who find themselves in need of it. In order to ascertain whether any of these rights are directly intended for women surviving violence we need to conduct a more detailed analysis of the Decisions, that is, we need to determine/map the conditions under which this type of service is provided.

3.7. Conclusion — overview of services for victims of violence (women surviving violence)

In the last chapter we mapped out social welfare services (defined by the Social Welfare Act) by reviewing and analyzing Decisions on Social Welfare Rights and Services that are available to citizens in 118 local government units (the number of local government units which provided documents in accordance with the request for public information, out of a total of 174 local government units on the territory of the Republic of Serbia). We mapped said services in order to determine which ones are intended for women surviving violence, and which ones are intended to the wider public (and where women surviving violence are recognized as one of the priority categories), in local government units as well as the whole country.

Before we set out to provide an overview of services intended for women surviving violence, we must note again the limitations faced in gathering and analyzing data: absence of a single, unified classification system of services (on the national level), differently defined and classified services in various local government units.

When it comes **to daily services in local government units, it was determined that none of them have this type of service intended for women surviving violence**. They can use some of the daily services — such as help and care at home — as members of other beneficiary categories (based on age, illness, disability). If they have a child with disabilities they (along with every other person of a local government unit) can use the service of a child's personal companion (pursuant to the conditions defined for that service).

The analysis of **support services for independent living** shows that there is **only one service that is directly intended for women victims of violence and their children** (as well as victims of trafficking), that being the service of housing which is provided for by the city of Zrenjanin. Even though this service is provided in 57 local government units, only one is intended directly for women surviving violence and their children (but not for victims of trafficking). Also, (general) **victims of violence are noted as beneficiaries of social housing in protected circumstances in 6 units of local government**, more specifically: persons who suffer domestic violence (city of Belgrade, Uzice, Pozarevac); victims of sexual or family violence (Prijepolje, Smederevo); victims of domestic violence (Trgoviste). Women surviving violence can access other services for independent living, just as can any other citizen, pursuant to predefined conditions. These services are personal assistant (for people with disabilities), social entrepreneurship, associations for the mentally disabled, translation services for sign language for people with disabilities, training for independent living, and if the woman has a child with disabilities she can use additional support in relation to her child's education (in group, or at school).

In relation to **counseling-therapy and socio-educational services** we must note the already mentioned limitations (given in section 3.4). The following services were mapped: socio-educational services, counseling services, therapy services, mediation, mobile teams for emergency interventions, SOS phone line for victims of violence, and other services. **Only 1 local government unit explicitly noted women with experience of gender-based violence** as a beneficiary group of this service (that being, SOS phone line for women with experience of gender based violence in the municipality of Cajetina), **while 4 local government units** (Babusnica, Bogatic, Dimitrovgrad and Zitiste) name **victims of violence in general as the beneficiaries**. Also, victims of violence in general (among others) are listed as beneficiaries of consultation services in 15 local government units. Victims of violence in general are also listed as beneficiaries in only 1 out of 12 units of local government which offer the services of mobile teams for emergency interventions. Women surviving violence have access to other services based on the fact that they are residents of the local government units (the same as all other citizens who reside there), pursuant to predefined conditions.

Accommodation services mapped in local government units fall under the following categories: accommodations in a halfway house/halfway station, safe house for victims of violence, temporary and sporadic accommodation and other services. This category of services also has **the biggest number local government units that offer a service specifically to victims of violence specifically**. When it comes to accommodation in a halfway house/halfway station, this service has been mapped in 90 local government units, but **in 19¹⁹ it is offered specifically to women victims of violence**. In 50 local government units victims of violence in general are recognized as the intended beneficiaries of this service. It remains unknown whether in the situation where a victim of violence is defined as a beneficiary of said service, he or she is placed in the same halfway station as people from all other categories, or not? Also, some local government units

19 Babušnica, Beocin, Dimitrovgrad, Jagodina, Kladovo, Knic, Knjazevac, Nis, Novi Sad, Rekovac, Titel, Kursumlija, Negotin, Nova Crnja, Svrlijig, Zabari, Leskovac, Secanj, Temerin.

refer to safe houses in other local government units as halfway houses/halfway stations. 12 local government units offer the service of placement to a safe house for victims of violence, and only 8 specifically note that it's intended for women and children in danger due to domestic violence (Belgrade, Kikinda, Pancevo, Ruma, Sremska Mitrovica, Vranje, Zrenjanin, Bor), while 4 offer it to victims of violence in general (Sabac, Smederevo, Subotica, Zajecar). Women surviving violence can access other services just based on the fact that they reside on the territory of a local government unit (the same as any other citizen), pursuant to predefined conditions.

In relation to the right to **financial aid** we found that the classification given in the Social Welfare Act differs from the factual financial aid types given out by local government units. As defined by the Decisions on Social Welfare Rights and Services which list an enormous number of, and widely diverse, financial aid services. We can roughly differentiate financial aid — money, aid in goods, reimbursement of expenses, and other rights. **Only 2 local government units give financial aid for victims of violence (in general), and those are the city of Belgrade and Pirot.** We would have to conduct a more thorough analysis of Decisions on Social Welfare Rights and Services so as to ascertain whether and under which conditions women surviving violence can access these services. In any case, these rights are available to them on the basis of the fact that they are citizens and reside on the territory of a specific local government unit (pursuant to predefined conditions).

Analysis of all decisions on the rights and social welfare services shows that there are only a few services which are directly intended for women surviving violence. They are not recognized as the beneficiaries for certain services, but what is available to them are accommodation services (halfway houses and safe houses). Other rights and services are intended for a wider range of beneficiaries or the overall population living on the territory of a certain local government unit. What is evident is that even for those few services (that the European Convention on Preventing and Combating Violence against Women and Domestic Violence) which are considered to be specialized services for domestic violence victims (SOS lines, safe house and halfway house accommodation) do not fulfill the standards set out in relation to (geographical) availability (Article 18). It's still an open question how accessible these services are for women from (multiple) marginalized groups.

Decisions on Social Welfare Rights and Services represent the basis for their exercise in practice so it remains to be seen how these services are developed in practice, whether there is a plurality of service providers, what is the level of service quality and professional work — all of which should be reviewed in detail in future analyses.

3.8. Recommendations

Analysis of the Decisions on Social Welfare Rights and Services has shown that social welfare services aimed directly at women who are surviving violence are not adequately developed, are not equally geographically distributed, and the lack of specialized services for women who have survived violence is evident. These conclusions are supported by data from the Decision on Social Welfare analysis produced by local municipal governments. There is an evident lack of development and accessibility of services for women who have survived violence and this issue has been confirmed by several analyses conducted on these topics. These analyses focused on the lack of specialized services intended for women victims of violence, as well as standards pertaining to geographic distribution (which have not been attained), and accessibility issues for women who belong to several marginalized groups. Women who have survived violence can use (urgent) shelter and safe house accommodation services, while a broader range of people (or possibly the whole populace of a specific municipal unit) are the intended recipients of other services. Therefore, in the goal of improving the process of identification and response to (specific) needs of women surviving violence (especially in regards to developing and ensuring rehabilitation and reintegration services) the social welfare system should: develop new specialized social welfare services for women who have survived violence, and improve existing ones based on research of their needs (primarily those women who are at greatest risk and are most vulnerable), and it should be done in accordance with good practice examples (from the EU and other countries). While creating, developing and implementing (new) services for women who have survived violence, attention must be paid to the following:

- That services are **available and accessible equally to women who belong to several marginalized groups** (especially women with disability, Roma women, and lesbians).
- That services are **adequately geographically distributed** in accordance to population density and the needs of women in specific municipal units.
- That services are **continuously and sustainably financed** from the budget; special attention should be paid to assuring that service provision is not restricted due to lack of finances, that is, that women themselves must not bear the brunt of the cost, and that services must not be “shut down” due to lack of finances.
- That women who have survived violence are **adequately informed about their rights and social welfare services they may access**, how to apply for said services, what documents they may need, and what the selection process entails (each municipality is responsible for informing women about this).

Additionally, it is necessary to:

- **Evaluate social welfare service implementation** so as to get feedback on the process and provision of social services, which will in turn further guide potential program improvement; also, record how effective and valuable the services were.

- Initiate **changes to the existing legal frameworks** of local municipal governments, and ensure that women who have survived violence are recognized as a specific target group/category when defining and while providing services which are aimed at a wider category of people (where there is a need for this).
- Establish a **uniform classification system of social welfare services** for the whole country (in regards to how services are defined, what they encompass, and category definitions).
- **Develop** and regularly update a **unified database/map of social welfare services** and make it available to the public (putting it online on local municipal government's web pages, web pages of the Ministry of Labor, Employment, Veterans and Social Affairs, and other relevant bodies and institutions). This database should also have sub-categories and search key words out of which one must be "services for women who have survived violence".
- **Make the existing positive-legal regulations publicly accessible and transparent** (those pertaining to social welfare units of local municipal governments). This should be uploaded online to web pages and/or other public platforms of local municipal governments.

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Decision on social welfare in Backa Topola municipality (“Official Gazette of Backa Topola municipality”, 9/2014)

Decision on social welfare rights and services on the territory of Bajina Basta municipality (“Official Gazette of Bajina Basta municipality”, 2/2013)

Decision on adopting the social welfare development strategy in Bajina Basta municipality from 2018 to 2022 (“Official Gazette of Bajina Basta municipality”, 6/2017)

Decision on social welfare in Batocina municipality (“Official Gazette in Batocina municipality”, 12/2012)

Decision on social welfare rights under the jurisdiction of Becej municipality (“Official Gazette of Becej municipality”, 18/2016)

Decision on social welfare rights and services in Bela Palanka municipality (“Official Gazette of the city of Nis”, 67/08, 2017, 2019)

Decision on social welfare in Beocin (“Official Gazette of Beocin municipality”, 6/2017)

Decision on changes and amendments to the Decision on social welfare in Beocin municipality (“Official Gazette of Beocin municipality”, 13/2017)

Decision on social welfare rights and services in the city of Belgrade (“Official Gazette of the city of Belgrade”, no. 55/2011, 8/2012 — changes, 8/2012, 42/2012, 65/2012, 31/2013, 57/2013, 37/2014, 82/2015, 4/2016, 37/2016, 56/2016, 114/2016, 102/2017, 50/2018, 103/2018 and 115/2019)

Decision on social welfare in Blace municipality (“Official Gazette of Blace municipality”, no. 1/20)

- Decision on social welfare rights and services of Bogatic municipality ("Official Gazette of the city of Sabac and municipalities of: Bogatic, Vladimirci, and Koceljeva", no. 32/2015 and 2017)
- Decision on social welfare and social security rights for citizens who are financed from the Bujanovac municipality budget ("Official Gazette of Bujanovac municipality", 2015)
- Decision on social welfare ("Official Gazette of Bor municipality", 13/2011)
- Decision on changes made to the Decision on social welfare ("Official Gazette of Bor municipality", 3/2015).
- Decision on amendments to the Decision on social welfare ("Official Gazette of Bor municipality", 3/2017).
- Decision on social welfare in Brus municipality ("Official Gazette of Brus municipality", 9/2013).
- Decision on changes and amendments to social welfare in Brus municipality ("Official Gazette of Brus municipality", 12/2013)
- Decision on changes and amendments to social welfare in Brus municipality ("Official Gazette of Brus municipality", 12/2020)
- Decision on social welfare rights and services in the jurisdiction of the city of Cacak ("Official Gazette of the city of Cacak", no. 2/2013, 22/2013 and 20/2016)
- Decision on social welfare in Cajetina municipality ("Official Gazette of Cajetina municipality", no. 2/2018)
- Decision on social welfare rights and services in Crna Trava municipality ("Official Gazette of the city of Leskovac", no. 29/2011, 27/2017 and 32/2019)
- Decision on social welfare in Dimitrovgrad municipality ("Official Gazette of the city of Nis", no. 70/11 and 27/13, 10/17, and "Official Gazette of Dimitrovgrad municipality", no. 17/18)
- Decision on social welfare in Doljevac municipality ("Official Gazette of the city of Nis", no. 22/18)
- Decision on expanded social welfare rights of citizens in Golubac municipality ("Official Gazette of Golubac municipality", 6/2013 and 2014)
- Decision on social welfare rights and services on the territory of Gornji Milanovac municipality ("Official Gazette of Gornji Milanovac municipality, no. 24/2011, 17/2016, 28/2016 and 1/2020)
- Decision on social welfare in Indjija municipality ("Official Gazette of Indjija municipality", 27/2018)
- Decision on social welfare in Irig municipality ("Official Gazette of Srem municipality", 6/2016)
- Decision on social welfare in the city of Jagodina ("Official Gazette of the city of Jagodina", no 15/2012, 6/2015, 27/2017 and 22/2018)
- Decision on social welfare services and financial support provided by Kanjiza municipality ("Official Gazette of Kanjiza municipality", 11/15 and 27/16)
- Decision on social welfare in the city of Kikinda ("Official Gazette of the city of Kikinda", no. 34/2017)
- Decision on social welfare rights and services in Kladovo municipality ("Official Gazette of Kladovo municipality", no. 2011)
- Decision on social welfare in Knic municipality ("Official Gazette of Knic municipality", no. 19/2018).
- Decision on social welfare in Knjazevac municipality ("Official Gazette of Knjazevac municipality", no. 9/2011)
- Decision on changes and amendments to the Decision on social welfare in Knjazevac municipality ("Official Gazette of Knjazevac municipality", no. 20/2013)
- Decision on changes and amendments to the Decision on social welfare in Knjazevac municipality ("Official Gazette of Knjazevac municipality", no. 20/2018)
- Decision on social welfare in Kosjeric municipality 2017 ("Official Gazette of Kosjeric municipality", 3/2017 and 30/2019)

Decision on social welfare rights and services on the territory of Kovacica municipality (“Official Gazette of Kovacica municipality”, no. 20/2016)

Decision on changes and amendments to the Decision on social welfare rights and services on the territory of Kovacica municipality (“Official Gazette of Kovacica municipality”, no 10/2017)

Decision on social welfare rights and services in Kovin municipality (“Official Gazette of Kovin municipality”, 18/2015)

Decision on social welfare in the city of Kragujevac (“Official Gazette of the city of Kragujevac”, no. 16/2011, 3/2016 and 34/2018)

Decision on social welfare in the city of Kraljevo (“Official Gazette of the city of Kraljevo”, no. 21/2017 and 22/2018)

Decision on changes and amendments on the Decision on social welfare in the city of Kraljevo (“Official Gazette of the city of Kraljevo”, no. 12/2011, 28/2012, 1/2013 — changes and 30/2014)

Decision on social welfare rights and services in Krupanj municipality (“Official Gazette of Krupanj municipality”, 30/2017)

Decision on social welfare rights and services in the city of Krusevac (“Official Gazette of the city of Krusevac”, no. 4/2013, 11/2013, 1/2014, 14/2016, 9/2017 and 13/2019)

Decision on the rights of citizens to social welfare on the territory of Kucevo municipality (“Official Gazette of Kucevo municipality”, no. 2018)

Decision on exercising the right to and accessing the services of social welfare in the jurisdiction of the municipality of Kula (“Official Gazette of Kula municipality”, no. 19/2014)

Decision on social welfare services (“Official Gazette of Kursumlija municipality”, no. 3/2012)

Decision on changes and amendments to the Decision on social welfare services in Kursumlija municipality (“Official Gazette of Kursumlija municipality”, no. 20/2016)

Decision on social welfare rights and services in Lajkovac municipality (“Official Gazette of Lajkovac municipality”, 6/2018)

Decision on changes and amendments to the Decision on social welfare rights and services in Lajkovac municipality (“Official Gazette of Lajkovac”, 8/2019)

Decision on requirements for, means of accessing and procedures of exercising the right to social welfare in Lapovo municipality (“Official Gazette of Lapovo municipality”, 4/2015)

Decision on social welfare on the territory of the city of Leskovac (“Official Gazette of the city of Leskovac”, 4/2014, 5/2015, 7/2017, 29/2017 I 2/2018)

Decision on social welfare rights and services in the city of Loznica (“Official Gazette of the city of Loznica”, no. 7/2017)

Decision on social welfare rights and services in Lucani municipality (“Official Gazette of Lucani municipality”, 10/2012)

Decision on changes and amendments to the Decision on social welfare rights and services in Lucani municipality (“Official Gazette of Lucani”, 12/2012)

Decision on changes and amendments to the Decision on social welfare rights and services in Lucani municipality (“Official Gazette of Lucani”, 12/2016)

Decision on changes and amendments to the Decision on social welfare rights and services in Lucani municipality (“Official Gazette of Lucani”, 12/2017)

Decision on expanded social welfare rights and services in Majdanpek municipality (“Official Gazette of Majdanpek municipality”, no. 17/11, 39/17, 18/18, 33/18, 24/19 and 36/19)

Decision on social welfare in Mali Idos municipality (“Official Gazette of Mali Idos municipality”, no. 16/2017)

Decision on changes and amendments to the Decision on social welfare in Mali Idos municipality (“Official Gazette of Mali Idos municipality”, no. 10/2018)

Decision on exercising the right to social welfare in Mali Zvornik municipality (adopted at a meeting of the Mali Zvornik Assembly on November 23rd, 2011)

Decision on changes and amendments to the Decision on exercising the right to social welfare in Mali Zvornik municipality (“Official Gazette of Mali Zvornik municipality”, no. 7/11 and 2017)

Decision on expanded social welfare rights and services of citizens in Malo Crnice municipality (“Official Gazette of Malo Crnice municipality”, no. 7/2019)

Decision on social welfare rights and services on the territory of Medveda municipality, and changes and amendments to that decision (“Official Gazette of the city of Leskovac”, no. 37/2016, 2018, and 2019)

Decision on social welfare in Merosina municipality (“Official Gazette of the city of Nis”, 47/2017)

Decision on changes and amendments to the Decision on social welfare in Merosina municipality (“Official Gazette of the city of Nis”, 134/2017)

Decision on social welfare in Negotin municipality (“Official Gazette of Negotin municipality”, 7/2012)

Decision on social welfare rights on the territory of the city of Nis (“Official Gazette of the city of Nis”, no. 101/2012, 96/2013, 44/2014, 118/2018, 18/2019 and 63/2019)

Decision on social welfare for citizens of the Nova Crnja municipality (“Official Gazette of Nova Crnja municipality”, 11/2011)

Decision on social welfare rights and services as provided by the Nova Varos municipality (“Official Gazette of Nova Varos municipality”, no. 2014)

Decision on changes and amendments to the Decision on social welfare rights and services as provided by the Nova Varos municipality (adopted on the Nova Varos Assembly meeting held on November 15th, 2019)

Decision on social welfare rights and services in the city of Novi Pazar (“Official Gazette of the city of Novi Pazar”, no. 2/2019).

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Decision on social welfare rights in the jurisdiction of Odzaci municipality (“Official Gazette of Odzaci municipality”, 20/2017)

Decision on social welfare in Opovo municipality (“Municipal Official Gazette of the municipality of Opovo”, no. 19/2012)

Decision on social welfare in Osecina municipality (“Official Gazette of Osecina municipality”, no. 3/2019)

Decision on social welfare of the citizens of the city of Pancevo (“Official Gazette of the city of Pancevo”, no. 38/2015, 32/2016, 7/2017 — changes, and 21/2018)

Decision on social welfare rights and services in Paracin municipality (“Official Gazette of Paracin municipality”, no. 8/2011 and 2/2012)

Decision on changes and amendments to the Decision on social welfare rights and services in Paracin municipality (“Official Gazette of Paracin municipality”, no. 17/2013)

Decision on changes and amendments to the decision on social welfare in Paracin municipality (“Official Gazette of Paracin municipality”, no. 4/2014, 13/2014 I 22/2014)

Decision on changes and amendments to the decision on social welfare in Paracin municipality (“Official Gazette of Paracin municipality”, no. 4/2015 I 5/2015)

Decision on changes and amendments to the decision on social welfare in Paracin municipality (“Official Gazette of Paracin municipality”, no. 1/2016 I 32/2016)

Decision on changes and amendments to the decision on social welfare in Paracin municipality (“Official Gazette of Paracin municipality”, no. 4/2017 I 18/2017)

Decision on social welfare in Pecinci municipality (“Official Gazette of Srem municipality”, no. 39/2011, 7/2013, 14/2015, 22/2018 — another provision, and 35/2018 — another provision)

Decision on social welfare in Petrovac na Mlavi municipality (“Official Gazette of Petrovac na Mlavi municipality”, 3/2017, 2/2018 and 9/2018)

Decision on social welfare in the city of Pirot (“Official Gazette of the city of Nis”, no. 2/2018)

Decision on social welfare of the citizens of the city of Pozarevac (“Official Gazette of the city of Pozarevac”, no. 4/2013 and 13/2013)

Decision on social welfare rights and services of the citizens of Prijepolje municipality (“Official Gazette of Prijepolje municipality”, 2/2016)

Decision on social welfare in the city of Prokuplje (“Official Gazette of the city of Prokuplje”, no. 27/2019)

Decision on social welfare of Raca municipality (“Official Gazette of Raca municipality”, no. 15/2019)

Decision on social welfare rights and services on the territory of Raska municipality (“Official Gazette of Raska municipality”, no. 165/2016)

Decision on social welfare in Razanj municipality (“Official Gazette of Razanj municipality”, 7/11, 2/14, 8/17 and 12/18).

Decision on social welfare in Rekovac municipality (“Official Gazette of Rekovac municipality”, no. 10/2011)

Decision on social welfare in Ruma municipality, basic provisions (“Official Gazette of Srem municipality”, March 2013)

Decision on social welfare rights and services in the city of Sabac (“Official Gazette of the city of Sabac and municipalities of Bogatic, Vladimirci, and Koceljeva”, no. 16/2018 and 29/2018)

Decision on social welfare in Senta municipality (“Official Gazette of Senta municipality”, no. 29/16)

Decision on social welfare rights and services on the territory of Sjenica municipality (“Municipal Official Gazette of Sjenica municipality”, no. 2/2014)

Decision on social welfare rights in the city of Smederevo (“Official Gazette of the city of Smederevo”, no. 2/2019 — amended text)

Decision on social welfare in Sokobanja municipality (“Official Gazette of Sokobanja municipality”, 40/2018)

Decision on social welfare rights in the jurisdiction of the city of Sombor (“Official Gazette of the city of Sombor”, no. 28/2016)

Decision on social welfare rights in Srbobran municipality (“Official Gazette of Srbobran municipality”, 2016)

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Decision on exercising social welfare rights in the jurisdiction of the city of Subotica (the decision was published in the “Official Gazette of the city of Subotica”, no. 40/2013, 15/2014, 7/2015 (Article 5. is not included in the amended text), 44/2016, 37/2017 and 35/2019)

Decision on social welfare in Stara Pazova municipality (“Official Gazette of Srem municipality”, no. 7/09, 8/12, 21/16, and 38/16)

Decision on social welfare rights and services in Svrlijig municipality (“Official Gazette of the city of Nis”, 78/2011, 51/2019)

Decision on social welfare in Temerin municipality (“Official Gazette of Temerin municipality”, no. 3/2014)

- Decision on social welfare in Titel municipality (“Official Gazette of Titel municipality”, no. 11/2013)
- Decision on financial support rights and social welfare services in Topola municipality (“Official Gazette of Topola municipality”, 10/2012, 12/2016)
- Decision on social welfare in Trgoviste municipality (“Official Gazette of the city of Vranje”, 2019)
- Decision on social welfare rights and services in Trstenik municipality (“Official Gazette of Trstenik municipality”, no. 2013)
- Decision on social welfare rights and services in Ub municipality (“Official Gazette of Ub municipality”, no. 5/2012)
- Decision on changes and amendments to the Decision on social welfare rights and services in Ub municipality (“Official Gazette of Ub municipality”, no. 9/2015)
- Decision on social welfare in the city of Uzice (“Official Gazette of the city of Uzice, no. 7/2015)
- Decision on social welfare in the city of Valjevo (“Official Gazette of the city of Valjevo”, no. 15/2019 — amended text)
- Decision on social welfare in Varvarin (“Official Gazette of Varvarin municipality”, no. 9/2012)
- Decision on social welfare in Veliko Gradiste municipality (“Official Gazette of Veliko Gradiste municipality”, no. 12/2018)
- Decision on social welfare in Vladicin Han municipality (“Official Gazette of the city of Vranje”, no. 28/2015, 4/2016 and 2017)
- Decision on social welfare in Vladimirci municipality (“Official Gazette of the city of Sabac, and Bogatic, Vladimirci and Koceljeva municipalities”, no. 2017)
- Decision on social welfare in Vlasotince municipality (“Official Gazette of the city of Leskovac”, 2018)
- Decision on social welfare in the city of Vranje (“Official Gazette of the city of Vranje”, no. 44/2016, 8/2018 and 16/2019)
- Decision on social welfare in Vrnjacka Banja municipality (“Official Gazette of Vrnjacka Banja municipality”, 16/2011)
- Decision on budget implementation of Vrnjacka Banja municipality in relation to expenditures pertaining to social welfare services in 2018 (“Official Gazette of Vrnjacka Banja municipality”, 39/2017)
- Decision on social welfare rights and services in the city of Vrsac (“Official Gazette of Vrsac municipality”, no. 16/2011 i 11/2014 and “Official Gazette of the city of Vrsac”, no. 18/2016 and 7/2018)
- Decision on social welfare in Zabalj municipality (“Official Gazette of Zabalj municipality”, 11/2011, 23/2012, 18/2014, 24/2014, 29/2015, 27/2016, 11/2017, 15/2019)
- Decision on social welfare rights and services in Zabari municipality (“Official Gazette of Zabari municipality”, 4/2012)
- Decision on social welfare rights and services in Zagubica municipality (“Official Gazette of Zagubica”, 10/2011)
- Decision on social welfare of citizens on the territory of the city of Zajecar (“Official Gazette of the city of Zajecar”, no. 31/2013 and 3/2016)
- Decision on social welfare on Zitiste municipality (“Official Gazette of Zitiste municipality”, 24/2011)
- Decision on social welfare rights and services in the city of Zrenjanin (“Official Gazette of the city of Zrenjanin”, no. 16/2017 and 18/2019 — second decision)

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